

Khupal 8: a high-yielding variety with good cooking quality for the mid-hill areas of Nepal

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Rice is the main crop in Nepal and it is cultivated at varying altitudes—from 60 masl in the Tarai (southern plain land) to 3,050 m in Jumla. Rice farming is considered prestigious in the hills and mountains and farmers prefer to grow rice even on a small piece of land or wherever it is possible to grow the crop. Rice is not only the staple food of the Nepalese people; rice straw is also a dependable source of cattle feed year-round. About 25% of the rice area is occupied by mid-hill rice and nearly 80% of this is covered by improved varieties (MOAC 2006). The most popular variety in this region is Khupal 4 (IR28/Pokhareli masino, a popular landrace of the hills), which lodges under fertile soil and high-input conditions. Therefore, farmers demand nonlodging varieties with quality traits of Khupal 4 and that fit well in the prevailing rice-wheat cropping system. The Agriculture Botany Division of the Nepal Agricultural Research Council (NARC) thus developed Khupal 8 derived from a cross between Jumli marsi (a local landrace for the high altitude) and IR36 (released by the National Seed Board for general cultivation in 2006).

Khupal 8 is a semidwarf variety (105.8 cm) that matures in 158 d and fits well in the rice-wheat system, the predominant cropping pattern in the Khet (bonded terrace) land of the mid-hills (Table 1). The cross was made in 1992 and the line was evaluated in an observation nursery in 1998. The initial evaluation trial was in 1999 and multilocation trials were conducted from 2000 to 2004 in four different locations from the eastern hills to the midwestern region of Nepal. It can be grown in medium-fertile to highly fertile soils. It has slender grain with white kernels and possesses good milling and cooking quality. The processed rice resembles Pokhareli masino. This nonlodging variety has shown field resistance to blast.

Table 1. Agronomic and grain quality characteristics of Khupal 8 in comparison with standard check Khupal 4.

Characteristic	Khupal 8	Khupal 4
<i>Agronomic</i>		
Plant height (cm)	105.8	138.4
Productive tillers plant ⁻¹ (no.)	10–15	9–12
Maturity (d after sowing)	158	144
Grains per panicle (no.)	110	122
1,000-grain weight (g)	23.4	18.9

<i>Quality</i>		
Milling recovery (%)	71.1	66.6
Head rice (%)	90.5	85.4
Kernel shape	Slender	Medium
Kernel length (mm)	6.66	6.02
Kernel breadth (mm)	2.19	2.17
Length/breadth	3.04	2.77
Amylose (%)	21.28	17.88

The performance of Khumal 8 under on-station (replicated multilocation) and on-farm (farmer-managed field) trials showed yield consistency and wide adaptability. Under farmers' management conditions, Khumal 8 gave an average yield of 5.8 t ha⁻¹, whereas check Khumal 4 yielded only 4.6 t ha⁻¹ (Table 2). Because of its high yield, lodging resistance, high milling recovery, and quality table rice (soft, fluffy, good taste, and feeling of “fullness” after eating), it is becoming popular in the central hills and is fast replacing the old variety Khumal 4.

Table 2. Performance of Khumal 8 rice variety at different locations, 2005.

Location	Region	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)		Percent superiority
		Khumal 8	Khumal 4	
Dhankuta	Eastern	5.5	4.3	27.9
Dolakha	Eastern	4.4	4.2	4.7
Khumaltar	Central	9.7	7.4	31.1
Lamjung	Western	5.1	3.9	30.7
Dailekh	Midwestern	4.3	3.3	30.3
Mean		5.8	4.6	24.9

References

MOAC (Ministry of Agriculture and Cooperatives). 2006. Statistical information on Nepalese agriculture, 2005-06. MOAC, Government of Nepal, Singh Durbar, Kathmandu.